

Inventory Management Analysis Using the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point, And Min-Max Stock Method at PT TTI

Muhammad Hizbullah Al Hakim¹, Triwulan Ari Saputro²

^{1,2}Master of Management, Widyatama University, Bandung, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 27 January 2026	This study aims to analyze inventory management by applying the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min–Max Stock methods to determine the optimal order quantity, reorder timing, and annual inventory cost estimation. The data used include an annual demand of 456 units, ordering cost of Rp255,529 per order, carrying cost of Rp110,638 per unit per year, daily usage of 2 units, and a 3-day lead time. The findings indicate that the optimal order quantity is 46 units per order, with a purchasing frequency of 10 times per year. The reorder point is set at 26 units, signaling the inventory level at which a replenishment order must be placed. The Min–Max analysis establishes a minimum inventory level of 26 units and a maximum of 72 units. Comparison of total inventory costs shows that the current company method results in total annual costs of Rp5,168,470, while the EOQ-based method yields a lower cost of Rp5,099,964. Thus, the application of EOQ–ROP–Min–Max provides annual savings of Rp68,506 and leads to a more efficient inventory control system by reducing both stock-out risk and excess inventory.
Corresponding Author: Triwulan Ari Saputro	
KEYWORDS: Inventory, Inventory Management, Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), Min-Max Stock	

I. INTRODUCTION

Inventory management is a strategic element in a company's operations, where effective inventory management implementation requires a balance between stock availability levels and the costs incurred. Excess inventory (overstock) leads to increased storage costs, risks of damage or expiration, and wastage of working capital. Conversely, insufficient inventory (stock-out) can disrupt operational smoothness, reduce service quality, and result in lost revenue opportunities.

To address these issues, various quantitative methods have been developed in the field of operations management to support inventory decision-making, including Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and the Min-Max Stock method. The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method is used to determine the optimal order quantity that minimizes total inventory costs, the Reorder Point (ROP) method establishes the appropriate time to reorder to avoid stock shortages, while the Min-Max Stock method sets minimum and maximum inventory limits as guidelines for controlling stock levels. Recent research indicates that implementing Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) can significantly reduce storage costs and the risk of stock shortages (Olaniyi & Pugal, 2024), while integrating

Reorder Point (ROP) improves order timing accuracy and inventory availability stability. On the other hand, the Min-Max method has proven effective in providing simple and measurable operational control, particularly in companies with high variation in spare parts requirements and relatively high unit values (Kamble, Gunasekaran, & Sharma, 2020).

Nevertheless, the partial application of inventory methods often faces limitations due to model assumptions that do not fully reflect actual operational conditions, such as demand uncertainty, variations in lead time, and complexities in supplier relationships. Therefore, an empirical evaluation of the effectiveness of combining Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min-Max Stock methods in the context of a specific company becomes crucial to ensure their relevance for cost efficiency and operational smoothness.

PT TTI is a company engaged in rotating equipment service, maintenance, and overhaul. Its operational activities heavily depend on the availability of spare parts and supporting materials. Inaccurate inventory quantities or delays in procurement can potentially hinder customer equipment maintenance and repair processes, reduce service reliability, and cause operational losses. This situation indicates a need

for an inventory control system capable of determining optimal order quantities, appropriate order timing, and rational minimum and maximum stock limits.

Based on this problem, this research aims to analyze inventory management at PT TTI using the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min-Max Stock methods. Specifically, this research aims to: First, evaluate inventory cost efficiency through the application of the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) method; Second, determine the optimal reorder point using the Reorder Point (ROP) method; and Third, establish appropriate minimum and maximum inventory limits through the Min-Max Stock method. Thus, the results of this research are expected to form the basis for formulating more effective inventory policies for PT TTI and provide an empirical contribution to the development of inventory management studies in the technical services industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Inventory

Margaretha (2011) defines inventory as raw materials, work-in-process, and finished goods maintained by a company to support the smoothness of operational activities in meeting consumer needs. This definition emphasizes that inventory is not limited to final products but encompasses all stages of the production process.

Herjanto (2014) views inventory as goods or materials stored for specific purposes, such as resale, production processes, and the provision of spare parts for machinery and equipment. Meanwhile, Sutarman (2017) explains that inventory relates to planning the quantity and timing of ordering raw materials or products optimally to support a company's operational activities. Furthermore, Schroeder, Goldstein, and Rungtusanatham (2022) explain that inventory functions as a buffer against demand uncertainty and procurement lead times, as well as a strategic instrument for maintaining a company's operational stability.

B. Factors Influencing Inventory

Margaretha (2011) defines inventory as raw materials, work-in-process, and finished goods maintained by a company to support the smoothness of operational activities in meeting consumer needs. This definition emphasizes that inventory is not limited to final products but encompasses all stages of the production process.

Herjanto (2014) views inventory as goods or materials stored for specific purposes, such as resale, production processes, and the provision of spare parts for machinery and equipment. Meanwhile, Sutarman (2017) explains that inventory relates to planning the quantity and timing of ordering raw materials or products optimally to support a company's operational activities. Furthermore, Schroeder, Goldstein, and Rungtusanatham (2022) explain that inventory functions as a buffer against demand uncertainty

and procurement lead times, as well as a strategic instrument for maintaining a company's operational stability.

C. Inventory Cost

The goal of inventory management is to provide the necessary inventory to guarantee the continuity of a company's operations at minimal cost (Sudana, 2011). Broadly, inventory costs generally include holding/carrying costs, ordering costs, and shortage/stockout costs. These three components are interrelated in determining the optimal inventory level that minimizes total overall cost (Martini et al., 2025).

- Holding costs refer to expenses related to maintaining inventory stock in warehouses and other storage facilities. This cost is generally expressed as a percentage of the average inventory value and is highly influenced by the amount of inventory stored.
- Ordering costs encompass all expenses incurred to order and receive inventory, including administrative, transportation, goods inspection, and related handling costs.
- Shortage costs arise when inventory is insufficient to meet customer demand or production needs.

D. Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) Method

Harmono (2014) defines EOQ as a method for determining the most economical purchase quantity so that a balance between these two types of costs can be achieved. A similar concept is put forward by Heizer and Render (2015), who state that EOQ is a mathematical model to help companies determine the order size that yields minimum inventory costs.

Conceptually, EOQ is based on the trade-off relationship between ordering costs and holding costs. Ordering in small quantities with high frequency increases ordering costs, while ordering in large quantities raises holding costs due to increased average inventory in the warehouse (Sartono, 2017). Therefore, there is an equilibrium point where total inventory cost is at its lowest level, and this point is called the economic order quantity. Mathematically, EOQ is formulated as follows (Russell & Taylor, 2006):

$$EOQ = \sqrt{\frac{2DS}{H}}$$

Where:

- EOQ = Economic Order Quantity
- D = Annual demand quantity
- S = Ordering cost (per purchase order)
- H = Annual holding cost per unit

The application of the EOQ method is based on several basic assumptions, including constant demand, known and fixed procurement lead time, orders arriving all at once, no

quantity discounts, and no stockouts (Heizer & Render, 2011). These assumptions make EOQ relatively easy to apply and suitable for use in stable operational environments.

E. Reorder Point (ROP)

ROP is defined as the minimum inventory level that signals when a company must immediately reorder before stock is completely depleted, taking into account needs during the procurement lead time (Heizer, Render, & Munson, 2020). This concept emphasizes the importance of synchronizing demand rate and supply speed to minimize the risk of stockouts or excessive stock accumulation.

Quantitatively, ROP is calculated based on the average demand during lead time plus safety stock to anticipate demand uncertainty and supply delays. The general formula used to calculate the Reorder Point is as follows:

$$ROP = d \times L + SS$$

Where:

- ROP = Reorder point
- d (demand) = Average daily demand quantity
- L (Lead Time) = Time required by the supplier to deliver new stock
- SS (Safety Stock) = Reserve stock to anticipate uncertainties

F. Min-Max Stock Method

The Min-Max method aims to maintain the continuity of raw material availability while controlling storage costs to prevent excessive inventory accumulation (Heizer, Render, & Munson, 2020).

Conceptually, the minimum inventory in the min-max method functions as a safety margin to anticipate demand uncertainty and supply delays during lead time. When the inventory level reaches this minimum limit, the company must immediately reorder a sufficient quantity to raise stock to the maximum limit (Silver, Pyke, & Thomas, 2017).

Determining parameters in the min-max method generally begins with calculating safety stock, which reflects strategic reserves to cover fluctuations in material usage. Subsequently, the minimum inventory is determined as the quantity needed during lead time plus safety stock, while the maximum inventory is set as the optimal stock level capable of meeting the needs for two order periods plus safety stock (Zipkin, 2019). This calculation structure shows that the min-max method is closely related to the Reorder Point concept, as the minimum limit essentially represents the reorder point.

The quantitative calculation of this method is generally formulated as follows:

- Safety Stock = (Maximum usage - Average annual usage) × Lead time (in months).

- Minimum Inventory = (Average annual usage × Lead time) + Safety Stock.
- Maximum Inventory = 2 × (Average annual usage × Lead time) + Safety Stock.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Type

This research uses a descriptive and analytical quantitative approach, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of applying the Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min-Max Stock methods in inventory control. This approach allows the researcher to analyze the relationship between inventory control methods and dependent variables, namely cost efficiency, stock availability, and operational smoothness.

B. Research Location and Subject

The research was conducted at PT TTI, located in West Java, Indonesia, a company engaged in the repair, maintenance, and overhaul of rotating equipment. The research subjects include the logistics, accounting, and purchasing divisions responsible for managing and recording spare parts and supporting material inventory.

C. Population and Sample

The research population includes all materials and spare parts recorded in the company's inventory system during the 2024 period. The sampling technique uses purposive sampling, with criteria:

- Materials or spare parts frequently used in repair service and maintenance.
- Materials with significant economic value for the company.
- Materials with regular ordering frequency and complete records.

D. Data Collection Technique

Data was collected through a combination of:

- Internal company documentation, such as inventory reports, order history, ordering costs, inventory costs, and warehouse records.
- Direct observation of the storage system and procurement process.
- Semi-structured interviews with logistics, purchasing, and accounting staff to obtain information related to the inventory management practices used.

E. Data Analysis Method

Data were analyzed using a quantitative approach and comparative analysis:

- EOQ calculation is mathematically formulated as follows (Russell & Taylor, 2006):

“Inventory Management Analysis Using The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point, and Min-Max Stock Method at PT TTI”

$$EOQ = \sqrt{\frac{2DS}{H}}$$

Where:

EOQ = Economic Order Quantity

D = Annual demand quantity

S = Ordering cost (per purchase order)

H = Annual holding cost per unit

- The formula used to calculate Reorder Point (ROP) is as follows:

$$ROP = (d \times L) + SS$$

Where:

ROP = Reorder point

d (demand) = Average daily demand quantity

L (Lead Time) = Time required by the supplier to deliver new stock

SS (Safety Stock) = Reserve stock to anticipate uncertainties

- The Min-Max Stock Method calculation is formulated as follows:

- Safety Stock = (Maximum usage - Average usage) × Lead time.
- Minimum Inventory = (Average usage × Lead time) + Safety Stock.
- Maximum Inventory = 2 × (Average annual usage × Lead time) + Safety Stock.

IV. RESULTS

In its repair and maintenance service activities, PT. TTI uses various types of inventory raw materials. Based on interview results, the inventory item with the most significant value and frequent use is Gas Argon HP 6M3. These inventory are used in the GTAW (Gas Tungsten Arc Welding) and GMAW (Gas Metal Arc Welding) welding repair processes.

For the calculation, the following is the data collected through internal company documentation, observation, and interviews:

Table 1. Purchase and Sales / Usage of Gas Argon HP 6M3

Item Type	Purchase	Purchase Frequency	Sales / Usage
Gas Argon HP 6M3	470	51	456

Table 2. Ordering Cost for Gas Argon HP 6M3

Ordering Cost Item	Cost/Year (IDR)	Cost/Order (IDR)
Purchase administration cost	6,600,000	129,412
Loading & receiving inspection	6,000,000	117,647
Telephone & internet cost	432,000	8,471
Total	13,032,000	255,529

Table 3. Holding Cost per Cylinder per Year for Gas Argon HP 6M3

Holding Cost Item	Cost/Year (IDR)	Cost per Cylinder/Year (IDR)
Electricity cost	600,000	15,319
Building insurance cost	433,333	11,064
Warehouse maintenance	3,300,000	84,255
Total	4,333,333	110,638

Table 4. Lead Time, Daily Usage and Safety Stock for Gas Argon HP 6M3

Data Type	Unit	Amount
Delivery lead time	Days	3
Daily usage (d)	Cylinder	2
Safety stock (SS)	Cylinder	20

Based on the results of the collected data, the following are the calculation results:

EOQ (Economic Order Quantity) Calculation

$$EOQ = \sqrt{\frac{2DS}{H}}$$

$$= \sqrt{((2 \times 456 \times 255,529) / 110,638)}$$

$$= \sqrt{(233,053,968 / 110,638)}$$

$$= \sqrt{2,106.5}$$

$$= 46 \text{ units per order}$$

The value of 46 units indicates the purchase quantity that minimizes total inventory cost, where:

- If the company buys fewer than 46 units, orders become too frequent, causing ordering costs to rise.

“Inventory Management Analysis Using The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point, and Min-Max Stock Method at PT TTI”

- If it buys more than 46 units, average stock increases, leading to higher holding costs.

EOQ becomes the basis for determining an economical and consistent lot size for each order.

Order Frequency

$$\text{Frequency} = D / \text{EOQ}$$

$$= 456 / 46$$

$$= 9.9 \approx 10 \text{ orders per year}$$

Order Interval

Working days / frequency = 240 / 10 = 24 working days per order.

This means, if daily consumption is constant, the company will place orders on average every 3–4 weeks.

Total Inventory Cost (TIC)

Table 5. Comparison of Total Inventory Cost

Method	Annual TIC	Difference
Company's Method (Q=38)	Rp5.168.470	Lebih mahal
EOQ Method (Q=46)	Rp5.099.964	Lebih efisien
Savings	Rp68.506	per tahun

Reorder Point (ROP) Calculation

$$\text{ROP} = \text{Safety Stock} + (\text{Daily usage} \times \text{Lead time})$$

$$\text{ROP} = 20 + (2 \times 3)$$

$$\text{ROP} = 26 \text{ units}$$

When stock drops to 26 units, an order must be placed immediately.

Reorder Point (ROP) Components:

- 6 units are used to meet demand during lead time (2 × 3)
- 20 units serve as safety stock for demand fluctuations

The Reorder Point (ROP) practically prevents stockout conditions while waiting for goods to arrive.

Min–Max Stock Level Calculation

The Min–Max policy sets two inventory control limits:

- Minimum Stock (Min) = reorder point + safety stock
- Maximum Stock (Max) = maximum stock level that should be available after an order arrives

General formula:

$$\text{Min} = \text{ROP}$$

$$\text{Max} = \text{ROP} + \text{EOQ}$$

Substitution:

$$\text{Min} = 26 \text{ units}$$

$$\text{Max} = 26 + 46 = 72 \text{ units}$$

Operational Significance

- When stock drops to 26 units, an order must be placed.
- After the goods arrive, inventory will return to 72 units.

$$\text{TIC} = (S \times D/\text{EOQ}) + (H \times \text{EOQ}/2)$$

Total Inventory Cost (TIC) for Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) Method

$$\text{a. Ordering cost} = 255,529 \times 10 = \text{IDR } 2,555,290$$

$$\text{b. Holding cost} = 110,638 \times (46/2) = \text{IDR } 2,544,674$$

$$\text{Total TIC} = 2,555,290 + 2,544,674 = \text{IDR } 5,099,964 \text{ per year}$$

Total Inventory Cost (TIC) for Company's Current Method

(Assuming current order quantity Q=38 based on data patterns)

$$\text{a. Ordering cost} = 255,529 \times 12 = \text{IDR } 3,066,348$$

$$\text{b. Holding cost} = 110,638 \times (38/2) = \text{IDR } 2,102,122$$

$$\text{Total TIC} = 3,066,348 + 2,102,122 = \text{IDR } 5,168,470 \text{ per year}$$

- The system oscillates between 26 and 72 units throughout the year.

Characteristics of the Min–Max System:

- Determines maximum storage space requirements.
- Regulates a consistent ordering cycle.
- Prevents excessive holding costs due to overstocking.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Economic Order Quantity (EOQ)

The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) forms the basis for deciding how many items to order each time a purchase is made. With a calculated result of 46 units, it is evident that ordering in lots larger than this value potentially increases holding costs due to inventory accumulation. Conversely, ordering smaller quantities increases order frequency and adds administrative and transaction costs.

With an order frequency of approximately 10 times per year, the company can predict ordering cost budget requirements more systematically. EOQ also helps convert purchasing decisions into data-driven actions.

B. Analysis of Reorder Point (ROP)

The analysis indicates that an order should be placed when the inventory level reaches 26 units. The Reorder Point (ROP) concept is crucial when a company faces non-instantaneous lead times, where goods do not arrive immediately after an order is placed.

With a lead time of 3 days and stable consumption of 2 units per day, the usage stock of 6 units during the waiting period for goods arrival must be safeguarded by an additional

safety stock of 20 units. Without safety stock, even minor disruptions such as a sudden demand increase, supplier delays, or transportation issues could potentially lead to uncertainty in fulfilling customer orders.

C. Analysis of Min–Max Stock

The Min–Max Stock approach provides a more visual control framework regarding the minimum and maximum limits of inventory that should be stored.

With Min = 26 units and Max = 72 units, the inventory management system will operate within this safe range. As long as stock remains above the minimum number, no ordering action is required. When stock touches the lower limit, ordering 46 units ensures inventory is replenished to the maximum point. The Min–Max approach is beneficial for:

- Managing warehouse capacity and avoiding overload.
- Controlling working capital so it is not locked up in inventory not immediately used.
- Creating a more regular ordering rhythm for vendor negotiations and logistics.

In distribution or retail company environments, min–max often becomes a tangible SOP in warehouse operations because it is easily translated into barcode systems, stock cards, or simple ERP systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion results, this research proves that the integrated application of Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min–Max Stock methods can improve the effectiveness and efficiency of inventory control for Gas Argon HP 6M3 at PT TTI. The calculation results show that the optimal order quantity is 46 units per cycle with a frequency of approximately 10 times per year, resulting in lower total inventory costs compared to the company's previous policy.

Setting the reorder point at an inventory level of 26 units has proven to provide protection against the risk of stockouts during the lead time period while maintaining the continuity of the welding production process. Meanwhile, the Min–Max Stock policy with a minimum limit of 26 units and a maximum of 72 units provides a clear operational framework for controlling inventory quantity, enabling the company to avoid both overstocking and stock shortages.

Overall, the quantitative approach through a combination of Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point (ROP), and Min–Max Stock methods not only contributes to inventory cost savings but also enhances operational certainty, working capital turnover efficiency, and the quality of managerial decision-making. Therefore, this method is worth recommending as a basis for establishing systematic and sustainable inventory policies, especially for industrial service companies with relatively stable demand patterns

and high dependence on the availability of supporting materials.

REFERENCES

1. Chopra, S., & Meindl, P. (2019). *Supply chain management: Strategy, planning, and operation* (7th ed.). Pearson Education.
2. Harmono. (2014). *Financial management based on balanced scorecard: Theoretical approach, case studies, and business research*. Bumi Aksara.
3. Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2011). *Operations management* (10th ed.). Pearson Education.
4. Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2015). *Operations management* (11th ed.). Salemba Empat.
5. Heizer, J., Render, B., & Munson, C. (2020). *Operations management: Sustainability and supply chain management* (13th ed.). Pearson Education.
6. Herjanto, E. (2014). *Operations management* (3rd ed.). Grasindo.
7. Kamble, S. S., Gunasekaran, A., & Gawankar, S. A. (2020). Achieving sustainable performance in a data-driven agriculture supply chain: A review for research and applications. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 219, 179–194.
8. Kasmir. (2010). *Introduction to financial management*. Kencana Prenada Media Group.
9. Margaretha, F. (2011). *Financial management for non-financial managers*. Erlangga.
10. Martini, N. N. S., Kaparang, R. M., Limpeleh, R. H. S. D., & Panelewen, S. S. (2025). Analysis of merchandise inventory management at PT Pusaka Agro Tani. *Politeknik Negeri Manado*.
11. Olaniyi, O. A., & Pugal, P. S. (2024). Optimising inventory management strategies for cost reduction in supply chains: A systematic review. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Bisnis: Jurnal Program Studi Akuntansi*, 10(1), 48–55.
12. Raisa, R., Salsabila, N., Fitriana, F., Yani, S. A. A., & Yulaeli, T. (2023). *Factors influencing inventory: Merchandise, raw materials, profitability, liquidity, FIFO method, and working capital*. Universitas Bhayangkara Jakarta Raya.
13. Rangkuti, F. (2017). *Inventory management: Business applications*. Raja Grafindo Persada.
14. Russell, R. S., & Taylor, B. W. (2006). *Operations management: Quality and competitiveness in a global environment* (5th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
15. Sartono, A. (2017). *Financial management: Theory and application* (4th ed.). BPFE.
16. Schroeder, R. G., Goldstein, S. M., & Rungtusanatham, M. J. (2022). *Operations management in the supply chain: Decisions and cases* (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.

“Inventory Management Analysis Using The Economic Order Quantity (EOQ), Reorder Point, and Min-Max Stock Method at PT TTI”

17. Silver, E. A., Pyke, D. F., & Thomas, D. J. (2017). *Inventory and production management in supply chains* (4th ed.). CRC Press.
18. Sudana, I. M. (2011). *Corporate financial management: Theory and practice*. Penerbit Erlangga.
19. Sutarman. (2017). *Fundamentals of logistics management*. Refika Aditama.
20. Syaifuddin. (2008). *Inventory management*. RajaGrafindo Persada.
21. Zipkin, P. (2019). *Foundations of inventory management* (2nd ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.